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Influence of Deposition Time on The Band Edge Position of α -Fe₂O₃ Photoanode

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ABSTRACT: The optical properties of semiconductors can be manipulated by varying the deposition time. However, reducing the deposition time may result in lowering the PEC performance of the fabricated photoelectrodes. In this work, the study aims to investigate the influence of deposition time on the optical band edge position of the fabricated α -Fe₂O₃ photoanode in a very short deposition period below 10 minutes. The α -Fe₂O₃ film was fabricated by aerosol-assisted chemical vapor deposition (AACVD). The XPS analysis confirmed the existence of Fe and O elements. The UV-vis showed that all deposited α -Fe₂O₃ films exhibit the absorption band in the visible-light region with the estimated energy bandgap of 2.10 eV. The Mott-Schottky plot demonstrated that the flat band potential value reduces with increasing deposition time which resulted in the shifting of the band edge position of α -Fe₂O₃. This shows that even the deposition time underwent below 10 minutes' deposition, yet it still can produce good PEC performance.

Keywords: α -Fe₂O₃, Photoanode, Band edge position, Photoelectrochemical, Aerosol-assisted chemical vapor deposition

1. Introduction

Hydrogen generation via photoelectrochemical (PEC) water splitting has attracted heavily attention due to its excellence potential to overcome the world's energy crisis and promote sustainability towards eco-friendly renewable energy sources in the future [1]. PEC water splitting is an electrode system constructed using specialized semiconductors that converts solar energy into a storable chemical constituents (H₂ and O₂) from the dissociation of water molecules [2–4]. In order for water to split effectively, the minimum energy required to drive the reaction is 1.23 eV [5]. Therefore, semiconductor materials must have the ability to absorb sunlight in the range of 400 nm – 800 nm in order to drive water splitting effectively [5,6].

The use of hematite (α -Fe₂O₃) as an electrode in PEC system has gained heavily attention due to its good thermodynamic stability, non-toxicity, low cost and abundance [7]. α -Fe₂O₃ is an n-type material having an optical band gap energy ranging between 1.9 – 2.2 eV, which can allow the utilization of approximately 40% of solar energy [8]. However, α -Fe₂O₃ experiences poor photo response due to high resistivity and charge recombination. In addition, the low charge mobility and short carrier diffusion length (2–4 nm) are another issues experienced by hematite which in turn limits its photoactivities to occur efficiently [9,10]. Since the water splitting process depends strongly on the optical functions of the fabricated electrode, therefore, the preparation method is seemly important to provide an excellent light absorption.

Aerosol-assisted chemical vapor deposition (AACVD) is considered as an attractive option for the films fabrication due to facile process, easy to operate, versatile and most importantly easy to control the desired morphology and film growth [10–12]. By using AACVD, study showed that prolonging the deposition time improves the light absorption which eventually reduces the optical band gap of α -Fe₂O₃ [10]. Therefore, this paper reports the influence of deposition time towards the optical band edge tuning via AACVD. The new idea of this work is to demonstrate that the band edge position particularly the conduction and valence band of n-type α -Fe₂O₃ is changing accordingly to the deposition time which becoming one of the factors that affect the efficient photoelectrochemical performance of α -Fe₂O₃. Hence, the α -Fe₂O₃ film was fabricated by employing the AACVD with deposition time of 2, 5 and 10 minutes at 450 °C. Then, the elemental composition and optical properties were thoroughly examined.

2. Methodology

Initially, fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) glass substrate was cut into (1 cm × 2 cm) and cleaned ultrasonically for 15 minutes in ethanol, isopropanol and acetone. The precursor, solvent and procedure used to fabricate the α -Fe₂O₃ photoanode are described in [10]. In this work, the samples are subjected to fabricate for 2, 5 and 10 min

deposition time at 450 °C. Then, all samples underwent XPS measurement using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy Model (Axis Ultra DLD) with Al K α X-ray gun was performed to analyze the band structure and elemental composition. The UV-Vis spectrometer (Lambda 35, PerkinElmer) was employed to analyze the absorption spectra of the films with the wavelength range applied from 300 – 700 nm. The PEC measurements were carried out on 1 cm² active area with a three-electrode configuration system including Ag/AgCl reference electrode, Pt electrode and the α -Fe₂O₃ fabricated electrode as working electrode. The measurements were performed in 0.5 M Na₂SO₄ (pH 7) electrolyte under solar simulator (1 Sun illumination = 100 mW cm⁻²) with an applied potential ranging from -0.2 V to +1.23 V vs Ag/AgCl. Mott-Schottky measurement was performed using similar PEC system to determine the flat band potential and Nyquist plot, respectively, with the 1 kHz applied frequency.

3. Results and discussion

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was used to identify the surface electronic structure and elemental composition of fabricated α -Fe₂O₃ films by AACVD. Overall, the XPS survey spectrum of α -Fe₂O₃ revealed that the sample has the composition of Fe and O elements as this can be seen in **Fig. 1(a)**. This figure indicates that the AACVD process at 450 °C is sufficient to completely convert the Fe-based precursor to α -Fe₂O₃. **Fig. 1(b)** shows the high resolution of Fe 2p spectrum with two satellite peaks observed at 707.08 eV and 720.71 eV originated from Fe 2p_{3/2} and Fe 2p_{1/2}, respectively. The energy difference between these two peaks is 13.6 eV as this indicates the presence of Fe³⁺ oxidation state in α -Fe₂O₃ [13,14]. Furthermore, there is no satellite peak was observed around 716 eV binding energy (i.e. the Fe²⁺ oxidation state) which strongly suggests the existence of a single phase α -Fe₂O₃ structure [15]. Other than Fe 2p peaks, the XPS spectrum also exhibited the O 1s satellite peaks at 526.1 eV and 527.6 eV as presented in **Fig. 1(c)**, showing the O²⁻ forming oxide with iron and OH⁻, respectively [13,16]. To gain some insight into the surface morphology of the prepared sample, **Fig. 1(d)** shows the FESEM image of the 10 min α -Fe₂O₃ film deposited by AACVD at 450 °C with 100 nm magnification scale. It is discovered that, with the rich amount of oxygen being supplied by purified air, the deposition caused the α -Fe₂O₃ film to grow vertically and it forms the uneven dense flake-like with a sharp apexes nanostructure. Furthermore, due to the random orientation of the nanoflakes, the film has more porous domain and slightly exposes the FTO surface. This phenomenon also discovered by [10,17] that the 10 min deposition via AACVD produced α -Fe₂O₃ film with vertically-aligned nanoflakes array in which the morphological structure later transformed into nanoflowers as deposition time is further extended.

Figure 1. (a) Full XPS survey spectrum, (b) Fe 2p XPS spectrum, (c) O 1s XPS spectrum of α -Fe₂O₃, and (d) FESEM image of α -Fe₂O₃ prepared for 10 min by AACVD.

The optical properties of the prepared samples are significant for PEC system as it determines the light absorption capability to the charge generation. In this work, the optical properties of α -Fe₂O₃ films were analyzed using UV-vis absorption spectrophotometer. **Fig. 2(a)** shows the absorbance spectra of α -Fe₂O₃ films recorded from 380 – 700 nm for 2, 5 and 10 min deposition time. In general, it can be observed that the absorption curves of all deposited α -Fe₂O₃ films exhibit an absorption band in the visible light region with the absorption onset at around 590 nm and the absorption intensity becomes more intense as it reaches around 400 nm. The enhancement of absorption edge of 10 min deposition is also recorded at $\lambda \approx 560$ nm which typically corresponds to spin-forbidden Fe(III) 3d → 3d transitions and the absorption of light starts to increase until lower wavelength [14]. In order to identify the optical bandgap (E_g) of α -Fe₂O₃, Tauc plot was used by extrapolating the absorption edge which derived by the following equation:

$$(\alpha h\nu)^n = A(h\nu - E_g) \quad \dots(1)$$

where α is absorption coefficient, $h\nu$ is photon energy, $n = 1/2$ (assuming a direct band gap material), A is constant and E_g is band gap energy. As can be seen in **Fig. 2(b)**, by plotting $(\alpha h\nu)^{1/n}$ against $h\nu$, it is estimated that the energy band gap of α -Fe₂O₃ for all samples is 2.1 eV which in a good agreement with the previous literature [18]. Therefore, the prepared α -Fe₂O₃ films by AACVD possess narrow band gap energy.

Figure 2. (a) Absorbance spectrum and (b) Tauc plot of α -Fe₂O₃ film prepared for 2, 5 and 10 min deposition time by AACVD at 450 °C.

Ideally, the band gap of semiconductor materials must be able to straddle the minimum and maximum redox potential at +0 and +1.23 V vs reverse hydrogen electrode (RHE). This means, the valence band (VB) potential must be more positive than O₂/H₂O redox potential of 1.23 V vs RHE (pH = 0), whilst, the conduction band (CB) potential must be more negative than H⁺/H₂ redox potential of 0 V vs RHE in order to carry out water reduction reaction [3]. **Fig. 3(a)** shows the Mott-Schottky plot of deposited α -Fe₂O₃ films that was carried out at 1 kHz frequency under dark conditions in 0.5 M Na₂SO₄ (pH 7) electrolyte. Overall, the positive slopes from all deposited samples indicate that α -Fe₂O₃ films exhibited n-type characteristics. In order to determine the energy band edge positions of deposited films, the flat band potential (V_{fb}) can be obtained from the intersection between x-axis and the extrapolated line where the values are applicable for estimating the conduction band (CB) of α -Fe₂O₃ [17,19]. In this case, the flat band potentials obtained from 2, 5, and 10 min deposition time are 0.07, 0.03 and 0.00 V (vs. Ag/AgCl) respectively. The measured flat band potentials can be converted to the RHE scale using the Nernst equation:

$$V_{RHE} = V_{Ag/AgCl} + 0.197 + (0.059 \times pH) \quad \dots(2)$$

and were recalculated as 0.69, 0.65 and 0.62 V vs. RHE respectively. Combining with the E_g obtained from the Tauc plot (**Fig. 2(b)**), the VB can be estimated using (CB = VB – E_g). **Fig. 3(b)** illustrates the estimated energy band diagram of α -Fe₂O₃ film deposited for 2, 5 and 10 min time. From this figure, it can be seen that the band edge positions increase with increasing of deposition time. The observation is also consistent with the improvement of photocurrent density as measured in 0.5 M Na₂SO₄ (pH 7) electrolyte under 1.5 AM solar simulator as shown by the J-V plot in **Fig. 3(c)**. This might be due to the shifting of the band edge position which resulted in good PEC performance although the energy band gap for all deposited films is the same.

Figure 3. (a) Mott-Schottky plot carried out at 1 kHz under dark conditions, (b) illustration of energy band diagram at 2, 5 and 10 min deposition time, and (c) J-V plot of α -Fe₂O₃.

4. Conclusions

The α -Fe₂O₃ film was successfully fabricated on the FTO by aerosol-assisted chemical vapor deposition (AACVD) at 450 °C with the supply of purified air. It is found that the deposition time affects the optical function of α -Fe₂O₃ photoanode. Despite of lowering the deposition time, the PEC performance shows a significant improvement in term of photocurrent density due to the increase of the band edge position even the band gap of all deposited samples below 10 min is the same.

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